

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BURLOT****FIRST NAME: MICHELE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is:

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In qualitative research, decisions about data collection methods should be guided by:
 - Your dissertation chair or advisor.
 - Your dissertation committee.
 - Your research questions.¹**
 - Your gut instinct.
2. When you select or are assigned a lead dissertation advisor, the advisor:
 - Must be an expert in your research topic.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End, 4th ed.* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, Inc., 2018), 259.

- Must be an expert in the dissertation process.²**
 - Must also be your second reader.
 - Must rotate the advisory position with a second reader.
3. When planning a poster presentation, remember:
- A poster is a cross between a talk delivered orally and a written paper.³**
 - A poster is an opportunity to present information not found in your written paper.
 - A poster is a copy of your PowerPoint presentation used in your oral presentation.
 - A poster is a prop used in your oral presentation.
4. Which statement below is one of the five basic objectives of research?
- Find a topic that you are passionate about, regardless of whether there is an audience for it.
 - Find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your reasons.⁴**
 - Stick as closely as possible to your first draft.
 - Use internet searches as your main source of finding information for your project.
5. The term reflexivity refers to:
- The practice of situating oneself within the context of the research.

² Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed.), 103.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 133.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed., 23.

- Reflecting on and critiquing one's own assumptions and biases.
- Showing awareness of, sensitivity to, and engagement with the cultural and social embeddedness of methods, theories, and research questions.
- All of the above.**⁵

6. In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, which of the following is true:

- It is necessary to cite at least 5 sources.
- It is important to list the title of the source parenthetically in the text of your paper.
- You must list sources in the references section according to publication date.
- You must list author names in the references section last name first for the first author and last name last for subsequent authors.**⁶

7. Why is the same source differently ordered and punctuated in Turabian's formats for notes and bibliographic entries?

- To give the reader the choice of how to look up an entry.
- Because notes and bibliographies are used for different purposes.**⁷
- Because it has always been done that way.
- To make sure the reader knows how to pay attention to detail.

8. A citation management tool such as Zotero is recommended in order to:

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed.), 46.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed., 244.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed., 155.

- Assist in keeping track of citations.
- Insert citations into a document.
- Insert a reference list or bibliography into a document.
- All of the above.**⁸

9. Qualitative research can best be described as:

- Addressing the questions of *what* and *how*.**⁹
- Addressing the questions of who, why, when, where, and what.
- Both of the above.
- Neither of the above.

10. If a Ph.D. student uses mixed methods research, which of the below is true:

- Their research must use at least five different methodologies
- Their research must use both quantitative and qualitative methodologies.**¹⁰
- Both of the above.
- Mixed methods research is not allowed.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed., 145-6.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed.), 135.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed.), 136.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.